

TA'LIM JARAYONIDAGI TEST EFFEKTI VA BOSHQA SOHAGA DOIR TERMINLAR TASNIFI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ta'lim jarayonidagi test tizimi effekti terminiga tadqiqotchilar ilmiy ishlaridan foydalangan holda tasniflar beriladi. Boshqa sohaga oid jarayondagi tushuncha va atamalar tasnifi va ularning qay yo'sinda aloqadorligi haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: test effekti, atamaning kelib chiqishi, keng ko'lamli test, sinovchilar, o'quv rejasini moslashtirish, tizimli asoslilik.

DEFINITION OF WASHBACK AND OTHER RELEVANT CONCEPTS

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Annotation: In this article the term washback will be evaluated and given different definitions by using world researchers' works. Other relevant concepts and terms will be investigated with definitions given by world scientists and the relevance of those concepts to washback system will be evaluated.

Key words: washback effect, the origin of the term, large-scale testing, test takers, curriculum alignment, systematic validity

КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ ТЕРМИНОВ, СВЯЗАННЫХ С ТЕСТОВЫМ ЭФФЕКТОМ В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОМ ПРОЦЕССЕ И ДРУГИХ СФЕРАХЮ

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Аннотация: В данной статье с использованием научных работ исследователей классифицируется термин эффект тест-системы в образовательном процессе. Существует мнение о классификации понятий и терминов в процессе, относящемся к другим областям и о том, как они связаны.

Ключевые слова: тестовый эффект, происхождение термина, крупномасштабное тестирование, тестировщики, адаптация учебного плана, систематическая валидность.

There are many educational terms and concepts in the world and they are being implemented into different spheres. Many terms are interconnected and function together. The term “washback” has different definitions given by world researchers. There have been different notions about that term and still yet to be finished. However, the main meaning given by nearly all scientists and linguists is similar but defines differently. Besides that, some definitions refer to only students and teachers whereas others include high level authorities such as educational systems. There is a natural tendency for both teachers and students to tailor their classroom activities to the demands of the test, especially when the test is very important to the future of the students, and pass rates are used as a measure of teacher success. This influence of the test on the classroom (referred to as washback by language testers) is, of course, very important; this washback effect can be either beneficial or harmful.[1] It can be seen

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that washback effect plays vital role in some educational systems as their result are the future of both test takers and teachers. Furthermore, it has pros and cons which depends on participants' attitude and studying style.

Shohamy also focuses on washback in terms of language learners as test-takers when she describes "the utilization of external language tests to affect and drive foreign language learning in the school context". She notes that "this phenomenon is the result of the strong authority of external testing and the major impact it has on the lives of test takers" . [2] From her concept, one can comprehend that washback is the result of testing on the lives of learners such as students.

Bachman and Palmer have discussed washback as a subset of a test's impact on society, educational systems, and individuals. They state that test impact operates at two levels: the micro level (i.e., the effect of the test on individual students and teachers) and the macro level (the impact on society and its educational systems).[3] The following comment from Buck illustrates how these two levels often work in tandem: Japan is a country in which the entrance examination reigns supreme. It is almost impossible to overstate the influence of these examinations on both the educational system as a whole, and the day-to-day content of classroom teaching. Their importance in the lives of young people is such that almost all future social and economic advancement is dependent on the results of these entrance examinations.[1] At this point, Bachman and Palmer tried to integrate and fill the definition of "washback" term by dividing into two operating categories: micro and macro level. This concept can be considered more powerful as it covers more areas such as students, teachers and society. Andrews sees washback as "a complex and ill-defined phenomenon" . He adds another dimension to the definition in terms of the scope of people influenced by test results, when he acknowledges "widespread acceptance of the assertion that tests, especially public examinations, exert an influence on teachers, learners, and parents, with an associated impact on what happens in classrooms". Andrews stresses the need for more research into washback, in order to better

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understand and manage the presumed influence of tests, particularly in the realm of promoting curricular innovation.[4] In his concept, he tries to urge researchers to investigate more to understand the real function of washback in education and other fields.

As we have mentioned above, there are several concepts relevant to washback effect. Shohamy summarized four key definitions that are useful in understanding the washback concept:

1. **Washback effect** refers to the impact that tests have on teaching and learning.
2. **Measurement driven instruction** refers to the notion that tests should drive learning.
3. **Curriculum alignment** focuses on the connection between testing and the teaching syllabus.
4. **Systemic validity** implies the integration of tests into the educational system and the need to demonstrate that the introduction of a new test can improve learning. [5]

We have already given different explanations for the term “washback effect” but still there are many concepts to be investigated. As Shohamy claimed tests should operate and have impact on learning which is one of the most important functions of tests. Furthermore, he emphasized that there must be close connection between test context and teaching plan. As a consequence, testing system will be beneficial and fruitful in terms of results. Last but not least, it is stated that the test context should prove itself as viable with concrete results in the end. Current test systems have different purposes such as testing learners’ ability, comprehension and others. If those tests are implemented into curriculum system efficiently, the final result will be as expected. By this way, test function will be fulfilled.

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